

Pedagogical Framework For Polyculturalism in Higher Education: Foreign Language Instruction

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ABSTRACT: The article highlights the theoretical and pedagogical frameworks for polyculturalism and multiculturalism as the foundational values attributable to future foreign language teachers in general and teachers, or instructors of languages for specific purposes, in particular. The findings substantiate the importance of pedagogical framework for poly- / multiculturalism given the fact that the created poly- / multicultural and polylingual environment of higher educational institution as a principle condition in value chain education may ensure the formation of poly- / multicultural personality of a foreign language teacher and LSP instructor. That becomes possible with the help of growing their socio cultural identity while students master the system of knowledge, concepts and ideas about poly- / multiculturalism in the poly- / multicultural environment of their classroom and improve social communication skills. It is stated that the complex of pedagogical conditions may well promote poly- / multiculturalism for future teachers of foreign languages and LSP instructors. It is underlined that pedagogical framework for polyculturalism in a foreign language classroom, aiming to teach philology students, rests on the following: (i) construction of training process in regards to foreign languages on the integration principle of educational disciplines with existing poly- / multicultural component according to tasks and the basic components of poly- / multiculturalism; (ii) application of interactive technologies for the formation of socio-cultural and poly- / multicultural competence, which includes bilingualism and poly- / multilingualism (didactic conditions); (iii) creation of a poly- / multicultural educational environment; (iv) dialogical interaction in the course of socio-cultural activities (educational conditions) *inter alia*.

KEYWORDS: polyculturalism, multiculturalism, polycultural values, foreign language teachers, languages for specific purposes (LSP), foreign language instruction, higher education.

INTRODUCTION

The focus on the internationalization of modern higher education in the context of globalization processes, of course, enhances the interaction of languages and cultures, which makes it necessary to develop students' ability to find themselves in professional contexts at the level of poly- / multicultural development and become aware of what makes them more efficient and progressive [1; 3; 10]. This involves foreign language communication skills and personal behavioural qualities, including the ability of poly- / multicultural individuals to understand the views and content of actions of other cultures, to adjust their behaviour to overcome conflicts and ensure effective communication, recognition of the right to different values and norms, including behaviourally and nationally marked specific forms of expression [15; 20; 21].

In terms of business communication, the question arises even sharper. The poly- / multicultural business environment requires not only mastery and / or high level linguistic competence and culture awareness, but also the knowledge-based skills in a professional domain [4; 16]. Next, it stretches much beyond that. The two challenges of linguistic and cultural nature trigger another connected with the didactics [5; 22]. It becomes critically important how to advance growth in the professional sphere with or without the training support [15]. This is a point under which the role of a foreign language teacher or a teacher in a core discipline assimilates or integrates with the role of a teacher or instructor of languages for specific purposes (LSP), which classes are deliverable in a language other than a mother tongue.

By differentiating between polyculturalism and multiculturalism and balancing between these two, it is polyculturalism that shapes its ways into the multinational foreign language classrooms when it comes to teaching languages for specific purposes. The point here is that multiculturalism aims to underline the importance of diversified interaction between the identities of self-identifying cultural groups, and its distinct feature links to separateness of such identities in order for them to preserve and celebrate their respective differences. At the same time, polyculturalism focuses on "similarities found between the self-identifying groups, which are comfortable with absorbing / eliminating elements of other culture(s) when acceptable and necessary for the identity, by blurring the ethnic / cultural boundaries of distinction between such members in the group" according to Chaika & Sharmanova (2021) in *Paremic Cliches as a Spiritual Layer of Multicultural Communication: Cultivating Respective Values for Educators*.

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With the term banks in a specific knowledge domain in various languages, languages for specific purposes share a great number of terms and terminological clichés / monomials and polynomials irrespective of the language selected. Most of the terms are accepted internationalisms or trace Latin and Greek origin, they may easily be recognized by polylingual speakers and degree seeking students, and teachers, and foreign language / LSP instructors, in a foreign language classroom for business or other purpose.

AIM OF THE PAPER AND OBJECTIVES, METHODOLOGY

Given the stated above, this paper considers the importance of pedagogical framework for higher education in the light of foreign language instruction of future philology teachers via polyculturalism/ multiculturalism. Foreign language instruction comprises a much broader understanding of the concept adoption associated with poly- / multiculturalism. The list of tools and methodology is as vast and diversified as the competence of a foreign language teacher may allow. With foreign language instruction of languages for specific purposes – English for Law, Ukrainian for Culture, Brazilian Portuguese for Cuisine, etc., it is polyculturalism that steps up to demonstrate language and culture tolerance and shared vision in the same professional domain of knowledge by the expert community, either existing or future.

Therefore, the objectives under the study refer to the below:

- Theoretical aspects of poly- / multicultural education in the higher educational establishments, on the one hand;
- Substantiation of the pedagogical framework for foreign language instruction via polyculturalism as the holistic pedagogical process and a critically valuable element in the pedagogical system of higher education, on another; and
- Description of the selected target components, which make part of the experimental model and involve the analysis of academic / educational, upbringing and developmental goals in the course of poly- / multicultural education of students, who are training to become future specialists in philology, foreign language instruction and translation.

Methodological input of the study in major part includes literature studies in the relevant fields locally and globally, by following similarities and differences in the research approaches and comparison of scholastic findings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The effectiveness of educating poly- / multiculturalism of future foreign language teachers and LSP teachers and instructors is due to a set of defined conceptual principles, goals, objectives, forms, and methods. What would drill deeper is the pedagogical framework for foreign language instruction in a multinational classroom, as well as instruction and acquisition of languages for specific purposes in higher education via polyculturalism. Largely, the pedagogical framework under study makes part of the holistic educational process, and stakeholders and other actors in higher education adopt such for organization of productive educational space to meet the job market demand for poly- / multicultural education of the today's students in both the segments – conventionally educational and business-oriented.

Thus, Gollnik understands multicultural education as an educational strategy, in which the cultural mentality of the subjects of education is seen positive and central in the organization of the learning process [12, p. 152]. Giroud takes that further when considers poly- / multicultural education as a process that significantly affects the individual development, i.e. it is a process caused by the interpersonal coexistence of two or more cultures [11, p. 282]. Suprunova connects the purpose of poly-/ multicultural education to formation of “a tolerant personality, which is able to actively interact with representatives of other ethnic cultures” [24, p. 52].

The literature review emphasizes the importance of considering the design and development of the pedagogical framework for foreign language instruction in general and that in instruction of languages for specific purposes via the lens of the needs borne by the Euro-integrating and globalizing processes in business, economics, and education [20; 21]. It means that the modern higher education should ensure the quality of smooth political and economic dialogues among the states and nation-states at the current stage and in future, correspondingly, via intercultural communication. The pedagogical framework for polylingualism and polyculturalism as the principal components of the poly- / multicultural education may help tailor cutting-edge technologies and methodology for future presentations of modern languages seen via cultures. In order to achieve that, it is necessary to take into account the existing pedagogical, cultural and informational prerequisites.

The literature study allows substantiating the pedagogical framework of poly- / multiculturalism for future teachers of foreign languages and languages for specific purposes in a foreign language classroom. It is found that philosophical, psychological and pedagogical works present the concepts of “pedagogical framework” differently. For instance, *Psychological Dictionary* defines the framework as “something that depends on something else, which makes the existence of a thing / state / process possible” and contrasts to the cause, which is “a logical condition of the consequence of action” [19, p.207].

Further, the dictionary of education and pedagogy defines “framework” as a set of variables in the natural, social, external and internal influences that produce physical, mental, moral development of man, their behavior; education and training, personality formation. Furthermore, the comprehensive dictionary of the modern Ukrainian language (2009) defines “framework” as “a necessary circumstance that enables the realization, creation, formation of something” and “circumstances, features of reality, under which something happens or is carried out” [7, p. 1506].

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Moving chronologically and following Antoniuk, Bukhlova, and Kostiuszko, Bakum and Pozhidayeva, the analysis of the scientific literature allows stating that the framework, pedagogical framework to be based on that definition, is seen a component of the pedagogical system as the holistic pedagogical process [2; 6; 16; 4; 18]. It is one of its elements; pedagogical conditions in the framework are a reflection of the set of possibilities expressly connected with educational, and material and spatial environment; pedagogical framework consists of internal and external elements. To this end, it is assumed internal elements affect the development of the personal area with subjects of the educational process. External elements, thus, contribute to the functioning of system processes; lastly, development and efficiency of the subsystem may be ensured by the implementation of appropriately defined pedagogical framework for foreign language instruction and instruction of languages for specific purposes (LSP) via polyculturalism and multiculturalism, and polyculturalism for the latter, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the material studied, the pedagogical framework arises as one of the components in the educational subsystem, which reflects the set of possibilities for educational and material-spatial environments. Educational and material-spatial environments affect the personal and procedural aspects of the subsystem and ensure its effective functioning and development.

It is found that the major pedagogical elements in the educational framework distinguish between the organizational and pedagogical, psychological and pedagogical didactic frameworks [4].

Thus, Pozhydaieva determines organizational and pedagogical framework as a created environment, in which a set of psychological and pedagogical factors appear in their interaction, which allows the teacher to effectively carry out educational or training work. Next, psychological and pedagogical framework is expected to provide certain measures of pedagogical influence on the development of the personality in regards to the subjects of the pedagogical process, which would lead to increased efficiency of the entire educational process. In the end, didactic framework includes certain learning circumstances that are the result of selection, design and application of elements of content, forms, methods and tools of learning that contribute to the effective solution of tasks [18].

In the context of poly- / multiculturalism in higher education for linguistic and other competences of future foreign language teachers and LSP instructors, it is determined that the pedagogical framework refers to the essence of this phenomenon in order to ensure maximum impact on the functioning of all its components. The latter include cognitive, axiological, communicative, self-regulatory, sociocultural, procedural and aesthetic components among the other things. At the same time, the content of the formulated pedagogical framework is expected to fit into the designed organizational and methodological system of professional training and education of future teachers in foreign language classrooms, including LSP instruction.

The main goal for the changing world, including the higher educational environment, is the education of poly- / multiculturalism in terms of immersion in the culture of the studied languages [8; 22; 15]. Therefore, the selection of the target component in the experimental model involves the analysis of educational, upbringing and developmental goals of poly- / multicultural education of such relevant students [3; 5; 10].

The educational goal is to ensure awareness (knowledge where appropriate) of poly- / multiculturalism as an integral quality of the subject of professional and pedagogical activities, which characterizes their professionally significant skills. The mentioned skills become the prerequisite that provides effective interaction in the context of intercultural business communication, in particular [22].

To be more specific, the educational goal is focused on the education of poly- and multiculturalism as an integral quality of the subject of professional and pedagogical activities. It aims at improving the general culture of students, i.e. their education, speech, culture awareness in two-way perspective – native and that of the selected languages for communication natural to the relevant peoples [10; 23]. It couples as a thinking and communication skill, which would expand their professional horizons in intercultural communication and in business.

The upbringing goal for poly- / multiculturalism of future teachers of foreign languages and LSP is focused on the formation of a positive perception of another culture, respect for its cultural values - along with a deeper understanding of native culture.

The developmental goals involve the harmonious development of the student's personality and their needs and aspirations for self-education in the polylingual and poly- / multicultural environment of the modern world [11; 25].

That above mentioned, it arrives appropriate to determine the following set of pedagogical frameworks: didactic, educational, and acmeological.

The didactic framework ensures the organization of the educational process for philology students, who are training to become future teachers of modern professional languages. Moreover, the content of disciplines then aims at poly- / multicultural and polylingual development of personality in the following areas:

- (i) Intellectual –the content plane forms culturological and linguistic knowledge;
- (ii) Spiritual and moral - the content plane forms the qualities of a poly- / multicultural diversified personality;
- (iii) Aesthetic - the content plane forms artistic and aesthetic attitude to artefacts and works of art associated with other cultures.

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The didactic framework of education in the field of culture for future teachers of foreign languages and LSP instruction defines the construction of the learning process of foreign languages on the principle of integration of disciplines with the presence of a poly- / multicultural component in accordance with the aim and objectives and main components of poly- / multiculturalism.

Polylingualism under the pedagogical framework for foreign language instruction via polyculturalism

One of the main criteria under the framework for the effective formation of a poly- / multicultural personality of a foreign language teacher and LSP instructor is language proficiency (polylingualism) and understanding of other cultures [18; 25]. At large, modern requirements for professionals have changed significantly. The contemporary political and business world as society needs citizens with a high level of poly- / multiculturalism, fluent in several languages, who are at ease with the moral values of world culture and understand the uniqueness of other cultures, tolerant of cultural diversity [20; 21]. To follow the line and meet the demand in communication locally and globally, the educational framework as an element in the pedagogical hierarchy is crucial these days.

The educational framework aims primarily at forming the qualities of the poly- / multicultural personality of the future teacher in foreign language instruction and LSP instruction in a foreign language classroom. Such qualities and properties include humanitarian attitude to universal values, dialogical thinking, tolerance, and poly- / multicultural identity, for example. With the help of the dialogue, the students and in future relevant teachers become able to actively interact with representatives of other cultures, to fully find themselves in the global world, regardless of nationality and cultural affiliation.

The educational conditions for the formation of poly- / multiculturalism of future teachers of foreign languages and LSP subjects determine the need in the following:

- Creation of a poly / multicultural educational environment at a university or other institution;
- Dialogical interaction in the process of socio-cultural activities in extracurricular activities.

Zelenska notes that the specially organized pedagogical framework will promote education of professionally significant qualities of the teacher in foreign language and LSP instruction in higher education [26].

The stated above leads to the following intermediary conclusions.

In a polylingual educational space, a poly- / multicultural personality is an active speaker of several languages. This is a person, who has a set of psychophysiological properties, which allow an individual to carry out language activities simultaneously in several languages. Secondly, this person has a set of abilities for verbal and non-verbal behavior and may use several languages as a means of communication with different linguistic societies. To implement the discussed, the following is seen required according to Dolhopolova:

- (a) Formation of knowledge / awareness culture, which provides an appropriate level of acquaintance with the cultural heritage of civilization and allows to adequately carry out creative activity in a poly- / multicultural space;
- (b) Development of a behavior culture, types and forms in accordance with the poly- / multicultural environment;
- (c) Formation of emotional culture (EQ) in accordance with the poly- / multicultural environment;
- (d) Formation of a culture of self-development in a poly- / multicultural environment [9].

The acmeological framework of education for poly- / multiculturalism of future foreign language and LSP teachers aims at stimulating and maintaining a high level of personal activity of students in the process of learning another culture and language, professional growth in the process of pedagogical reflection.

The acmeological framework for the education of multiculturalism of future foreign language and LSP teachers determine the need in the enlisted below:

- (a) Motivation and attitude to poly- / multicultural and polylingual self-development,
- (b) Readiness to master several languages;
- (c) Development of self-reflection of acquired knowledge and self-regulation of actions from the standpoint of norms and rules of intercultural interaction by means of application and with the help of coaching technologies.

In addition, Jessner reasonably underlines that the formation of personality includes the stage of accumulation of knowledge, feelings, and emotions caused by past events and phenomena. The knowledge and feelings become acquired linguistic and cultural experience and a source of establishing links between the individual and the world, culture, and him / herself. The acquired experience allows a person to understand the significance of each culture. As a result, there are active qualitative transformations of the inner world of the individual, leading to a new way of life - cultural self-realization [13].

Coaching technologies are critically important to help implement the pedagogical framework in higher education. Foreign language instruction and teaching languages for specific purposes can become an exciting learning journey with the coaching support in a multinational classroom. It is agreed with Alonso Alonso (2016) that the development of self-reflection, the formation of poly- / multicultural thinking contributes to the use of coaching technologies in intercultural communication, which involves the introduction of specific mental operations and develops students' ability to reconstruct this activity. It is a prerequisite for understanding the values and motives from the standpoint of norms and rules of intercultural interaction [1].

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CONCLUSION

To summarize, the education processes with the poly- / multicultural personality of a modern foreign language teacher and/or LSP instructor concentrates on broad communicative interaction with representatives of other language cultures; it involves strengthening the axiological attitudes and personality traits; it encourages and fosters formation of unlimited worldview, a broad understanding of the phenomena of human life.

It is obvious that the mastery and linguistic competence of a foreign language by students who are learning to become future teachers of modern languages and/or LSP teachers should have a fundamentally new character and be a universal tool for poly- / multicultural education.

When deciding on the education of poly- / multiculturalism for foreign language instruction, it is necessary to keep in mind that with the development of international contacts in the field of higher education, the relevance of research in this area increases significantly. The modern labor market has a specific aim, i.e. the training of a specialist who does not only have a high level of training, but also is ready for fruitful work in a poly- / multicultural world. The university in these conditions should, of course, take into account the new requirements and focus on them in the training of a competent specialist. It looks feasible by meeting the didactic, educational, and acmeological goals under the pedagogical framework for foreign language instruction via poly- / multiculturalism in a multinational classroom in higher education.

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